

Effect of Salinity on Germination Related Parameters of Linseed Genotypes (*Linum usitatissimum* L.) under Control Condition

Hosna Kohinoor ✉

Senior Scientific Officer, Oilseed Research Centre, Bangladesh Agricultural Research Institute,
Gazipur-1701, Bangladesh

N. A. Sultana

Senior Scientific Officer, Oilseed Research Centre, Bangladesh Agricultural Research Institute,
Gazipur-1701, Bangladesh

Shamsun Nahar Mahfuza

Senior Scientific Officer, Plant Physiology Division, Bangladesh Agricultural Research Institute,
Gazipur-1701, Bangladesh

Md. Milon Mia

PhD Researcher, Bangladesh University of Professional, Mirpur Cantonment, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Abul Kashem Chowdhury

Professor, Department of Genetics and Plant Breeding, Patuakhali Science and Technology University,
Dumki, Patuakhali, Bangladesh

Abstract

Salinity is one of the important abiotic stresses causing impairment in germination of seeds. An *in-vitro* experiment was conducted under controlled conditions to determine the effects of salinity stress on germination of linseed genotypes (*Linum usitatissimum* L.). A total of 29 linseed genotypes were evaluated under five salinity levels (0, 4, 8, 12 and 16 dS m⁻¹) created by NaCl. Six germination related traits such as final germination percentage (GP), salt tolerance index (STI) of GP, mean daily germination percentage (MDG), germination initial time (GIT), maximum germination time (MGT) and germination duration time (GDT) were studied. Wide variations were recorded in the responses of the genotypes to salinity stress in terms of these traits. The GP, STI and MDG were reduced over control at different salinity levels. The reduction in GP ranged (2.09-14.54%), (8.38-27.28%), (10.48-48.28%) and (15.77-76.35%) with pooled mean of 7.66, 14.55, 26.63, 44.28 and 23.28% at 4, 8, 12 and 16 dS m⁻¹, respectively. The reduction in MDG ranged (0.54-35.12%), (0.71-45.43%), (0.21-37.84%) and (3.07-69.14%) with pooled mean of 14.54, 21.04 and 36.32% at 4, 8, 12 and 16 dS m⁻¹, respectively. The highest pooled mean of STI was found in BD-10708 (89.55%) which was statistically similar to Lin-1403 (88.08%) and Lin-W-17 (86.04%), while the lowest STI was recorded from BD-10710 (62.81%) which was statistically similar to Lin-V-16 (67.25), Lin-1303 (67.63%) and Lin-2403 (67.68%). So, BD-107808, Lin-1403 and Lin-W-17 were noted as the most salt tolerant genotypes. Responses of GIT, MGT and GDT were not consistent with salinity levels and genotypes.

Keywords: Salinity stress, flax, germination, linseed.

Suggested citation: Kohinoor, H., Sultana, N.A., Mahfuza, S.N., Mia, M.M., & Chowdhury, A.K. (2026). Effect of Salinity on Germination Related Parameters of Linseed Genotypes (*Linum usitatissimum* L.) under Control Condition. *European Journal of Ecology, Biology and Agriculture*, 3(1), 15-28. DOI: 10.59324/ejeba.2026.3(1).02

Introduction

Linseed (*Linum usitatissimum* L.) is an annual herbaceous plant belonging to the family Linaceae. It is one of the oldest and industrially important crops. The seeds of linseed may be used to make a healthy diet because these are rich in omega-3 fatty acids, vitamins, minerals and dietary fiber. Seeds contain 35–40% oil. The oil is used in production of paints, varnishes, printing inks, cosmetics and oilcloths. The oil is also quite fit for human consumption. Linseed oilcake is a valuable ingredient of feed of fast growing animal and poultry (Kumar et al., 2019 & Al-Madhagy et al., 2023).

Salinity is a common abiotic stress affecting various aspects of plant development, especially germination, vegetative growth and reproduction. Salinity causes ion toxicity, osmotic stress, nutrient deficiency and oxidative stress on plants, and affects water and nutrient uptake from soil. Seed germination is the first stage of the plant's life cycle, which is negatively affected by salinity. Salt stress causes delay in germination and emergence, reduction in germination rate, high seedling mortality, poor crop stand and stunted plant growth resulting in poor crop yields (Kaya et al., 2012, Day et al., 2018, Moghaddam et al., 2018 & Ali et al., 2022).

Generally, seed germination, seedling growth and seedling vigor are considered very crucial traits for crop productivity in salt stressed soils (Zaghdoudi et al., 2015 & Day et al., 2018). In response to salt stress, the plant must develop adaptive mechanisms to adjust the pressure. Adaptation to salinity stresses is related to salinity tolerance levels of plants for germination and metabolic adjustments through diverse mechanisms (Zaghdoudi et al., 2015, Moghaddam et al., 2018 & Kaya et al., 2012). If the adverse effect of salt stress at the germination phases can be mitigated, it is possible to grow an optimum number of healthy plants per unit area to ensure profitable production. The best way to grow satisfactory populations of a crop in a saline prone region, with very little input cost involvement, is to grow salt tolerant crops or crop varieties.

A large area of coastal regions of Bangladesh is affected by salinity (Ahsan, 2010). In these areas, only *Aman* rice can be successfully grown mainly in rainy season. After harvesting *Aman* rice, vast areas of cultivable lands remain fallow due to saline problem and lack of salt tolerant crops or crop cultivars. Thus, a salt tolerant crop species or variety is required to grow there after *Aman* rice. Linseed has been identified as a moderately salt tolerant crop and suitable for cultivation in low saline soils (Day et al., 2018). The crop may be a good choice for saline region of the country if salt resistant varieties are available.

The widely used approaches to develop stress tolerant crop varieties are selection and hybridization programs. The foremost requirements of such approaches are identification of genetically diverse genotypes of the crop. The general approach of screening crop genotypes for salinity resistance or tolerance is growing them in salt affected soils and studying their growth and yield related traits. However, selection of a salt tolerant genotype based on germination and seedling growth under controlled conditions is simple, quick, precise and less time consuming but effective (Kaya et al., 2012).

Considering the above facts, the present investigation was conducted to study the effect of salinity stress on germination related traits of linseed genotypes under controlled condition.

Materials and Methods

Experimental Materials and Salinity Levels

A total of 29 linseed genotypes with diverse origins were tested in the experiment. Of these 14 genotypes (Neela, BD-7141, BD-7142, BD-7143, BD-7146, BD-10703, BD-10704, BD-10706, BD-10707, BD-10708, BD-10709, BD-10710, BD-10698, BD-10696) were obtained from Plant Genetic Resource Center (PGRC) and 10 genotypes (Lin-303, Lin-503, Lin-703, Lin-803, Lin-1203, Lin-1303, Lin-1403, Lin-1903, Lin-2403, Lin-1503/2) from Oilseed Research Center (ORC) of Bangladesh Agricultural Research Institute (BRAI), Gazipur, Bangladesh. Two genotypes Chilhari and Lin-S-19 were collected respectively from farmers of Rangpur and Satkhira districts of Bangladesh. Origins of other 3 genotypes (Lin-C-16, Lin-V-18 and Lin-1507/2) were China, Vietnam and Thailand, respectively. The genotype, Neela is a recommended linseed variety for cultivation in Bangladesh, which was used as a check material.

The levels of salinity maintained in the experiment were 0 (control), 4, 8, 12 and 16 dS m⁻¹. Common salt (NaCl) produced by natural evaporation of saline water was dissolved in sterilized distilled water to have salt solutions with required salinity levels. Salinity level of the NaCl solution was measured with an EC meter (Model: Hanna, DIST-4).

Location and Design of Experiment

The experiment was conducted in the Laboratory of Oilseed Research Center (ORC) of Bangladesh Agricultural Research Institute (BARI), Gazipur during winter season (December to January) of 2019-2020. It was a 29x5 factorial experiment in a completely randomized design with four replications (Petri dishes).

Establishment of Experiment

Seeds of selected genotypes were surface sterilized with 0.5% Chlorox (NaOCl) for 10 minutes followed by rinsing with sterilized distilled water for three times. Surface sterilized seeds were placed on 2-ply filter paper disks in 90 mm Petri dishes and moistened with 10 ml solution of respective salt concentration. Each Petri dish received 25 seeds and 4 dishes (replications) were used for each genotype. Petri dishes were sealed with parafilm to prevent from drying. The Petri dishes along with seeds were placed on laboratory desks at room temperature (25°- 28°C).

Data Collection

The experiment was checked every 24 hours after incubation and continued for 5 days. Data on germination percentage (GP), Salt tolerance index (STI) of GP, mean daily germination percentage (MDG), and germination initial time (GIT) in days, maximum germination time (MGT) in days and germination duration time (GDT) in days were recorded. The GP, MDG, GIT, MGT and GDT were recorded according to Hefny et al. (2020). Salinity tolerance index (STI) of germination was computed following the procedures of Pervez et al. (2021).

(i) Germination percentage (GP)

$$GP = \frac{\text{Number of germinated seeds}}{\text{Total number of seeds plated}} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

(ii) Mean daily germination (MDG)

$$MDG = \frac{GP}{MGT} \quad (2)$$

(iii) **Germination initial time (GIT) in days:** GIT= Number of days to first appearance of germinated seed with 2 mm radicle.

(iv) **Maximum germination time (MGT) in days** = Number of days when the maximum number of germinated seeds appeared.

(v) **Germination duration time (GDT) in days**

$$\text{GDT}=\text{MGT}-\text{GIT} \quad (3)$$

(vi) **Salt tolerance index (STI)** - The salinity tolerance index of final germination percentage was computed according to Pervez et al. (2021) using following germination percentage:

$$\text{STI (\%)} = \frac{\text{Germination percentage at a salinity level}}{\text{Germination percentage under control}} \times 100 \quad (4)$$

Data Analysis

Collected data on different parameters were subjected to analysis of variance (ANOVA). The treatment means were compared using least significant difference (LSD) test at 5% probability level. All statistical analyses were performed using Statistix 10 computer software.

Results

Germination Percentage (GP)

Under control, the germination percentage (GP) of 29 linseed genotypes was varied from 76.65 to 98.33% with a mean of 90.89%. The highest GP was recorded from Neela and BD-10698, which were statistically similar to that of BD-7141, BD-7142, BD-7143, BD-7146, BD-10704, BD-10707, BD-10708, BD-10710, Lin-303, Lin-503, Lin-703, Lin-1203, Lin-1303, Lin-1403, Lin-2403, Lin-1503/2, Lin-1507/2, Lin-S-19, Lin-V-18 and Lin-W-17. The GP in these 22 genotypes ranged 90.00 to 98.33%. The lowest GP was recorded from Chilmari and Lin-C-17, which were statistically similar to Lin-C-16 (81.0%), Lin-1903 (82.0%), Lin-803 and BD-10703 (85.00%). The GP was 88.33% under control in BD-10706 (Table 1 - Appendix).

Salinity stress caused reduction in GP and the reduction was corroborated with salinity levels within the range of 4-16 dS m⁻¹. However, the reduction was significant at 8 dS m⁻¹ and higher levels of salinity in most of the genotypes compared to control (Table 1 - Appendix).

At the lowest level of salinity (4 dS m⁻¹), the GP of 29 genotypes was reduced to 70.00% (Chilmari) to 91.65% (BD-10698 and Lin-503) with a mean of 83.80%. At this level, significant (P<0.05) reduction over control was begun in 5 genotypes (Neela, BD-142, BD-7143, Lin-703, Lin-W-17). In other 24 genotypes, the GP under control and at 4 dS m⁻¹ was statistically similar (Table 1 - Appendix).

At 8 dS m⁻¹, the GP of 29 genotypes was further reduced over control to 60.00 to 88.35% with a mean of 77.70%. The reduction was significant in all genotypes except Lin-C-16 and Lin-S-19. The highest GP was found in BD-10698, which was statistically similar to Neela, BD-7146, BD-10708, Lin-1403, Lin-1203, Lin-W-17, Lin-503, BD-10704, BD-10707, Lin-1507/2, Lin-V-18, Lin-S-19, Lin-2403 and Lin-1503/2. These 15 genotypes showed 80.00-88.35% germination. The lowest GP was found in Chilmari

(60.00%), which was statistically similar to Lin-803 (61.65%), Lin-C-17 (65.03%), BD-10710 (66.65%) and Lin-1903 (66.68%). The GP in other eight genotypes ranged 71.65-78.35-% germination, which were not significantly different (Table 1 - Appendix).

At 12 dS m⁻¹, the GP was varied from 48.33 to 85.03% with a mean 67.10%. The parameter was significantly reduced over control in different genotypes. The highest GP was found in BD-10708 which was statistically similar to BD-10708, BD-10698, Lin-1403, Neela, Lin-1203, Lin-W-17, BD-10707, Lin-2403, Lin-1503/2, Lin-503, Lin-S-19, and Lin-1507/2. The lowest GP was found in Chilmari, which was not significantly different from Lin-1303, BD-7146, BD-10710, Lin-703, Lin-303, Lin-C-16, Lin-C-17, Lin-V-17, Lin-1903 and Lin-803 (Table 1 - Appendix).

At 16 dS m⁻¹, the GP of all genotypes was significantly reduced over control within the range of 21.68 to 80.00% with a mean of 50.60%. The highest GP was recorded from BD-10708 and Lin-1403 and the lowest from BD-10710. The second lowest GP was found in Lin-V-18 (33.32%) followed by Lin-803 (36.65%), BD-7146 and Lin-1903 (38.35%). In the rest 18 genotypes, the GP varied from 43.00 to 57.00% (Table 1 - Appendix).

The pooled mean of GP over five salinity levels in 29 genotypes varied from 59.67 (Chilmari) to 87.30% (BD-10708, Lin-1403). The highest pooled mean of GP was found in Lin-1403 and BD-10708 (87.33%) followed by BD-10698 (84.67%), Neela (84.00%), Lin-1203 (82.00%), Lin-W-17 (81.67%) and Lin-2403(80.00%). The lowest pooled mean of GP was found in Chilmari (59.67%), which was statistically similar to Lin-803 (62.00%), Lin-C-17 (63.00%), Lin-1903 (63.32%) and BD-10710 (63.33%). In other 17 genotypes, the GP ranged 65.67-79.0% (Table 1 - Appendix).

Mean Daily Germination (MDG)

Under control (0 dS m⁻¹), the maximum mean daily germination (MDG) was found in BD-10704 (31.0%), which was statistically similar to BD-7141 (30.00%), BD-7142 (30.55%), Lin-1503/2 (30.0%), BD-10710 (29.15%), BD-7146 (28.60%), and BD-10703 (28.35%). The lowest MDG was found in Lin-C-17 (19.15%), which was statistically similar to Lin-503 (20.68%), BD-10698 (20.83), Lin-W-17 (21.10%), and Lin-1507/2 (21.40%). In other 13 genotypes (Neela, BD-7143, Lin-1303, Lin-703, Lin-303, Lin-1403, Lin-1203, BD-10706, Lin-1507/2, Lin-V-18, Lin-S-19, Lin-803, and Lin-1903), the trait was varied from 22.50 to 25.70% and was not significantly different. Statistically similar MDG (26.10-27.30%) was also found in BD-10707, BD-10708, Lin-C-16 and Chilmari (Table 1 - Appendix).

The MDG was statistically similar at all salinity levels including control in only one genotype (BD-10706). In 19 genotypes, the trait was reduced over control significantly in parallel with salinity levels but considerable reduction was not started at the same level of salinity. The reduction was observed at all level (4, 8, 12 and 16 m⁻¹) in 8 genotypes (Neela, BD-10703, BD-10704, BD-10710, Lin-803, Lin-C-16, Lin-V-18 and Lin-W-17); at 8, 12 and 16 dS m⁻¹ in 5 genotypes (BD-7142, BD-10710, Lin-1303, Lin-S-19 and Chilmari); at 12 and 16 dS m⁻¹ in 6 genotypes (BD-7141, BD-7146, Lin-303, Lin-703, Lin-1403 and Lin-2403) and at 16 dS m⁻¹ in only Lin-1903 (Table 1 - Appendix).

The MDG was increased significantly over control at 4 and 8 dS m⁻¹ in BD-10708, at 4, 8 and 12 dS m⁻¹ in Lin-1203 and at 12 and 16 dS m⁻¹ in BD-10698 and Lin-503. In other 5 genotypes, the MDG was inconsistent, where it was increased at two lower levels in BD-7143, at the lowest level in BD-10710, Lin-1503/2 and Lin-C-17, and at 12 dS m⁻¹ in BD-10707 but at their other levels the trait was reduced due to the treatments compared to control (Table 1 - Appendix).

Salinity Tolerance Index (STI)

The salinity tolerance index (STI) of 29 linseed genotypes for germination percentage ranged (85.59-96.68%), (73.61-92.72%), (51.56-89.55%) and (24.11-84.31%) with a mean of 92.62, 85.79, 73.83 and 55.81%, respectively at 0, 4, 8 12 and 16 dS m⁻¹. In every genotype, the STI was the highest at 4 dS m⁻¹

followed by 8, 12 and 16 dS m⁻¹. Differences in the trait at 4 and 8 dS m⁻¹ were not significant in every genotype. At 12 dS m⁻¹, the maximum STI was found in BD-10708, which was statistically similar to Neela, BD-10698, BD-10703, BD-10704, BD-10706, BD-10707, Lin-503, Lin-803, Lin-1203, Lin-1403, Lin-1507/2, Lin-1903, Lin-S-19 and Lin-W-17. At this level, the minimum STI was found in Lin-1303, which was statistically similar to BD-7146, Lin-303, Lin-703, and Lin-V-18. In other 8 genotypes, the trait was also not significantly different among themselves at 12 dS m⁻¹ (Table 2 - Appendix).

At 16 dS m⁻¹, the maximum STI was recorded from BD-10708, which was statistically similar to Lin-1403. The third highest STI was recorded from BD-7141 (70.02%) followed by BD-10706, Lin-W-17, Neela, BD-10703, Lin-C-17, BD-10698 and Lin-1507/2. Differences in the trait in these 8 eight genotypes were not significant. The lowest STI was found in BD-10710, which was statistically similar to Lin-V-18. The third highest STI was recorded from BD-7141 (70.02%) followed by BD-10706, Lin-W-17, Neela, BD-10703, Lin-C-17, BD-10698 and Lin-1507/2. The genotypes, BD-7141, Lin-1203, Chilmari, Lin-1503/2, Lin-1903, Lin-803, Lin-S-19, Lin-C-16, Lin-303, BD-7143, Lin-703, BD-10707, BD-10704 and Lin-503 showed statistically similar STI. In other 4 genotypes (BD-7142, Lin-1303, Lin-2403, BD-7146), the trait was also not significantly different (Table 2 - Appendix).

The highest pooled mean of STI was found in BD-10708 (89.55%), which was statistically similar to Lin-1403, Lin-W-17, BD-10706, BD-10698, Lin-1507/2, Lin-1903, Neela, Lin-803, BD-10703, Lin-1203, Lin-503, Lin-S-19, Lin-C-16 and BD-10707. The lowest STI was recorded from BD-10710 (62.81%), which was statistically similar to Lin-1503/2, Lin-303, BD-7142, BD-7143, BD-7146, Lin-703, Lin-2403, Lin-1303, Lin-V-18 and BD-10710 (Table 2 - Appendix).

Germination Initial Time (GIT)

Germination was initiated within 2.00 days of sowing under control in all genotypes except Lin-C-16 and BD-10707. In these two genotypes, radicles appeared at 2.50 days and 2.25 days of incubation, respectively. Seeds of 13 genotypes (BD-7141, BD-7143, BD-7146, BD-10698, BD-10706, BD-10707, BD-10708, BD-10710, Lin-303, Lin-703, Lin-1303, Lin-V-18 and Chilmari) protruded 2 mm radicles within 2.00-2.25 days of sowing at different levels of salinity. In Lin-C-17, the GIT was delayed to some extent, where the radicle appeared within 2.50 days at 0, 4 and 16 dS m⁻¹ and within 2.25 days under 12 dS m⁻¹. In these 14 genotypes, the trait was statistically similar at all salinity levels including control (Table 2 - Appendix).

Compared to control, the initiation of germination was significantly delayed in Neela, Lin-C-17 and Lin-W-17 at 16 dS m⁻¹ and in Lin-503, Lin-1403 and Lin-2403 at 12 and 16 dS m⁻¹. Due to salinity stress, the GIT was significantly extended over control in 5 genotypes (BD-7142, BD-10703, BD-10704, Lin-1507/2 and Lin-1903) at only 8 dS m⁻¹; in Lin-1203 at 12 dS m⁻¹ and in Lin-S-19 at 8 and 12 dS m⁻¹. In Lin-803 and Lin-1503/2, the trait significantly increased at 8 and 16 d S m⁻¹ compared to control (Table 2 - Appendix).

Maximum Germination Time (MGT)

Under control (0 dS m⁻¹), the maximum germination time (MGT) varied from 3.00 to 4.75 days with a mean of 3.71 days among 29 genotypes. The lowest MGT (3.00 days) was recorded from 6 genotypes (BD-7141, BD-10703, BD-10704, Lin-C-16, Lin-1503/2 and Chilmari), which were statistically similar to the genotypes, BD-7142, BD-7146 and BD-10707 (3.25 days). The trait was 3.50 days in 4 genotypes (BD-7143, BD-10708, BD-10710, and Lin-1903) which were statistically similar to BD-10706 (3.75 days). The MGT was 4.00 days in Neela, Lin-303, Lin-703, Lin-1203, Lin-1303, Lin-1507/2, Lin-C-17, Lin-S-19 and Lin-V-18, which were statistically similar to Lin-1403, Lin-2403 and Lin-W-17 (4.25 days). The highest MGT was found in BD-10698 (4.75 days), which was significantly different from Lin-503 (4.50 days) (Table 3 - Appendix).

Response of MGT to salinity stress varied with the variation of genotypes and salinity levels. The trait was statistically similar under control (0 dS m⁻¹) and 4-16 dS m⁻¹ in four genotypes (BD-7142, BD-7146, Lin-1903 and Chilmari); and at 4-12 dS m⁻¹ in five genotypes (Lin-303, Lin-703, Lin-1303, Lin-1403 and Lin-C-17) (Table 3 - Appendix).

Compared to control, MGT was significantly reduced at 4-16 dS m⁻¹ in six genotypes (BD-7143, BD-10698, BD-10708, BD-10710, Lin-503 and Lin-1203); and at 4-12 dS m⁻¹ in only Lin-1903. These seven genotypes might be noted as highly adaptive materials in salinity stress condition (Table 3 - Appendix).

In response to salinity stress, the MGT was increased to 4.50-5.00 days in Neela, Lin-W-17 and Lin-2403 at 4-16 dS m⁻¹; in Lin-303, Lin-703, Lin-1303, Lin-1403 and Lin-C-17 at 16 dS m⁻¹; in Lin-C-16, BD-10707, BD-10706, BD-10704, BD-10703, Lin-S-19, Lin-V-18 and BD-7141 at 8 dS m⁻¹; in Lin-1503/2 at 8 and 12 dS m⁻¹ and in Lin-803 at 4, 8 and 16 dS m⁻¹. The increase in the trait of these 18 genotypes was significant compared to control (Table 3 - Appendix).

Germination Duration Time (GDT)

Under control, the germination duration time (GDT) varied from 1.00 to 2.75 days in 29 genotypes with a pooled mean of 1.66 days. The highest GDT was recorded from BD-10698 and the lowest from five genotypes (BD-7141, BD-7142, BD-7143, Lin-1503/2, Lin-C-15 and Chilmari). The trait varied from 1.00 to 1.25 days in 9 genotypes (BD-7141, BD-7142, BD-10703, BD-10704, BD-10707, BD-107010, Lin-1503/2, Lin-C-16 and Chilmari), 1.50 to 1.75 days in 5 genotypes (BD-7143, BD-10706, BD-10708, Lin-803, Lin-1903), and 2.00-2.25 days in the rest 14 genotypes (Neela, Lin-1303, Lin-703, Lin-303, Lin-1403, Lin-C-17, Lin-1203, Lin-503, Lin-1507/2, Lin-1507/2, Lin-V-18, Lin-W-17, Lin-2403). The difference in GDT of each of the three groups of genotypes was the same (0.25 days) and not significantly different (Table 3 - Appendix).

The responses of GDT of 29 linseed genotypes to salinity stress varied with the variation of salinity levels and genotypes. The trait was statistically similar at all salinity levels including control (0-16 dS m⁻¹) in 8 genotypes (BD-7142, BD-7146, BD-10703, BD-10704, BD-10710, Lin-1507/2, Lin-V-18, Chilmari). In five genotypes (Lin-303, Lin-703, Lin-1303, Lin-1403, Lin-C-17), the trait was also statistically similar at 0-12 dS m⁻¹ but significantly higher over control at the highest level (16 dS m⁻¹). On the contrary, the parameter was significantly reduced over control in six genotypes (BD-7143, BD-10708, Lin-1203, BD-10698, Lin-503 and Lin-1903) at 4-16 dS m⁻¹. In the rest 10 genotypes, the GDT was not consistent with salinity levels, where the trait was significantly increased over control in BD-7141, BD-10707, Lin-C-16, and Lin-S-19 at 8 dS m⁻¹; in Neela, Lin-W-17 and Lin-2403 at 4 and 8 dS m⁻¹; in Lin-1503/2 at 8 and 12 dS m⁻¹; and in Lin-803 at 4, 8, 16 dS m⁻¹. The parameter was significantly reduced over control in BD-10706 at 4, 12 and 16 dS m⁻¹. At other levels of salinity, GDT of these 10 genotypes was statistically similar to control (Table 3 - Appendix).

Discussion

The results of the present investigation revealed that the germination percentage (GP) of every genotype was the highest under control. Due to application of NaCl solution for soaking germination paper caused reduction in the trait over control in all genotype at all salinity levels. However, the significant reduction ($P < 0.01$) was started at 4 dS m⁻¹ in 5 genotypes (Neela, BD-7142, BD-7143, Lin-703, Lin-W-17), at 8 dS m⁻¹ in 22 genotypes (BD-7141, BD-7146, BD-0698, BD-10703, BD-10704, BD-10706, BD-10707, BD-10708, BD-10710, Lin-303, Lin-503, Lin-703, Lin-803, Lin-1203, Lin-1303, Lin-1403, Lin-1903, Lin-2403, Lin-C-17, Lin-V-18, Lin-W-17 and Chilmari) and at 12 dS m⁻¹ in 2 genotypes (Lin-C-16, Lin-S-19). Irrespective of beginning level, the reduction was continued in parallel with salinity levels showing the lowest GP at 16 dS m⁻¹. Reduction in pooled mean of germination percentage in 29 genotypes ranged (2.09-14.54%), (8.38-27.28%), (10.48-48.28%) and (15.77-76.35%) with a grand mean of 7.66, 14.55,

26.63, 44.28 and 23.28% at 4, 8, 12 and 16 dS m⁻¹, respectively. The reduction in pooled mean of GP was linear, positive and significantly correlated with concentration of NaCl ($r=0.981^{**}$). Their relationship could be explained by the regression equation $Y_{GP}=12.193+- 7.2045x$, where x represents salinity level and Y_{GP} represents estimated GP. Like GP, the mean daily germination percentage (MDG) was reduced due to salt stress at all salinity levels in 19 genotypes showing the lowest MDG at the highest salinity level. In these 19 genotypes, the reduction was ranged 0.67-35.12, 2.87-45.43, 10.46-48.90 and 17.85-69.14% with pooled means of 15.27, 20.63, 24.82 and 40.05% at 4, 8, 12 and 16 dS m⁻¹, respectively. In other 10 genotypes, the GDT was inconsistency with salinity levels. The pooled mean of reduction percentage was linear, positive and significantly correlated (0.921^{**}) with concentration of NaCl. The relationship could be explained by the regression equation $Y_{MDG}=6.575+6.90x$, where x represents salinity levels and Y_{MDG} represents estimated reduction percentage of MDG. In general, the STI was higher at lower salt concentrations. The influence of salinity on this trait was not significant at 4 and 8 dS m⁻¹, which indicated that tested genotypes were tolerant to salt stress for germination up to 8 dS m⁻¹. Significant reduction in STI occurred at 12 and 16 dS m⁻¹ indicating that tested genotypes could not withstand salinity stress above 8 dS m⁻¹.

The results on STI are in agreement with the reports of other investigators (Pervez et al., 2021; Yasar and Yetissin, 2023). Variations in germination related parameters with the variation of linseed genotypes under salinity stress have also been reported by Kaya et al. (2012), Pervez et al., 2021; Ali et al. (2022) and Kocak et al. (2022).

The findings of the present study are in agreement with the reports of many other investigators (Kaya et al., 2012; 2019 ; Zaghoudi et al., 2015; Nasri, et al., 2017; Day et al., 2018; Moghaddam et al., 2018, Abido and Zsombik, 2019; Ali et al., 2022; Kocak et al., 2022; Yasar and Yetissin, 2023), who also conducted experiments under controlled conditions to find out effect of salinity on germination characters of linseed. They found that salinity impaired germination, early seedling growth and germination time, and the degree of severity was directly correlated with levels of salinity. Mohammadi et al. (2023) and Kaya et al. (2019) found that salinity stress delayed the mean daily germination of fennel compared to control and the lowest values of this trait were observed at the highest salinity level. Reduction in mean daily germination percentage of lettuce due to salinity stress has also been reported by Nasri et al (2017).

Mechanisms of impairment in germination percentage and mean daily germination of linseed genotypes due to salinity stress have been discussed based on available literature. According to available recent literature, salt stress impairs seed germination through osmotic stress, ion toxicity, and oxidative stress, hindering water uptake, disrupting cellular processes, and causing cellular damage (Ucarli, 2020). Salinity causes osmotic stress by lowering the water potential of the germination medium in comparison to the seed interior and reduces or prevents the uptake of water (imbibition) necessary for mobilization of nutrient required for germination (Munns, 2008; Kaya et al., 2012; Kocak, et al., 2022; Mohammadi et al., 2023). Sometimes high salt stress causes absorption of too much Na⁺ and Cl⁻ ions by seeds resulting in ionic stress and ion toxicity to the embryo (Munns, 2008) and salinity causes imbalance of hormones especially gibberellic acid (GA) and abscisic acid (ABA), and seed nutrients like Na⁺ and K⁺ (Abbasian and Moemeni, 2013; Miransari and Smith 2014; Zaghoudi et al, 2015). Salinity may affect germination altering permeability of cell membrane and impairing water absorption at imbibition (Han and Yang, 2015, Ucer, 2020).

Germination initial time (GIT), maximum germination time (MGT) and germination duration time (GDT) are the three common germination related traits. In the present investigation these 3 traits were found to be significantly correlated among themselves. However, germination percentage was not significantly correlated with any of the three characters. The findings indicated that these three traits did not influence final germination percentage of linseed under salinity stress.

Results of the present investigation revealed that the GIT was not influenced by all salinity levels (4-16 dS m⁻¹) in 14 genotypes (BD-7141, BD-7143, BD-7146, BD-10698, BD-10706, BD-10707, BD-10708, BD-10710, Lin-303, Lin-703, Lin-1303, Lin-V-18, Lin-C-17 and Chilmari) as compared to control (0 dS m⁻¹). Probably, these genotypes possess highly effective adaptive mechanisms to withstand adverse effect of salinity stress up to 16 dS m⁻¹ (Muns and Tester, 2008 & Ucarli, 2020). The trait delayed considerably in six genotypes (Neela, Lin-C-17, Lin-W-17, Lin-503, Lin-1403 and Lin-2403) due to salinity stress at higher levels, which indicated sensitivity of these genotypes to salinity. In remaining 9 genotypes, the GIT was not consistent with salinity level.

The maximum germination time was not influenced by salinity stress in four genotypes (BD-7142, BD-7146, Lin-1903 and Chilmari) up to 16 dS m⁻¹, and in five genotypes (Lin-303, Lin-703, Lin-1303, Lin-1403 and Lin-C-17) up to 12 dS m⁻¹. The results indicated the existence of high salt tolerant characteristic in these 9 genotypes. The trait was significantly increased over control at all salinity levels (4-16 dS m⁻¹) in Neela, Lin-803, Lin-W-17 and Lin-2403; and at three higher levels in Lin-1503/2 indicating their sensitivity to salinity stress. The MGT was significantly reduced over control at all salinity levels (4-16 dS m⁻¹) in six genotypes (BD-7143, BD-10698, BD-10708, BD-10710, Lin-503 and Lin-1203) and at 4, 8 and 12 dS m⁻¹ in only Lin-1903. These seven genotypes might be noted as highly adaptive materials under saline stress conditions.

The responses of germination duration time (GDT) of 29 linseed genotypes to salinity stress varied greatly with genotypes and salinity levels. The influence of salinity on GDT was not significant in 8 genotypes (BD-7142, BD-7146, BD-10703, BD-10704, BD-10710, Lin-1507/2, Lin-V-18 and Chilmari) at 4-16 dS m⁻¹ and in 5 genotypes (Lin-303, Lin-703, Lin-1303, Lin-1403, Lin-C-17) at 4-12 dS m⁻¹. The findings indicated that these 13 genotypes were salt tolerant up to 12-16 dS m⁻¹. Influence of salinity on GDT was inconsistency with salinity levels in other genotypes

The findings of the present study revealed that the GIT, MGT and GDT of 29 linseed genotypes showed four distinct types of responses to salinity. The stress caused (i) no influence on the traits in some genotypes, (ii) increased in second group, (iii) decreased in third group and (iv) increased or decreased at a level but became statistically similar to the control in the next higher levels. Absence of influence of salinity on GIT, MGT or GDT under salinity stress may be attributed to the facts that these genotypes possess effective adaptive mechanisms to withstand adverse effect of salinity stress. Another fact may be that the salinity levels maintained (up to 16 dS m⁻¹) in the present investigation was not enough to cause significant effect on these 3 traits. The opinions are in line with the reports of other researchers (Zaghdoudi et al., 2015 & Kaya et al., 2019) who reported that linseed showed tolerant responses to salinity stress until 20 dS m⁻¹. Delay in germination time due to salinity stress has also been reported by Muhammad and Hussain (2010).

The increasing and decreasing trends found in GIT, MGT and GDT in some genotypes may be attributed to the variations in their adaptive mechanisms. Plants adapt to salinity stress using their inherent adaptive mechanisms in three ways: osmotic stress tolerance, toxic ions (Na⁺ or Cl⁻) exclusion, and the tolerance of tissue to accumulate Na⁺ or Cl⁻ ions (Munns and Tester, 2008 & Ucarli, 2020). According to Han and Yang (2015) germination is under strict regulation of plant hormones, especially gibberellic acid (GA) and abscisic acid (ABA). The ABA promotes seed dormancy and restricts germination of seed but GA breaks dormancy and enhances germination. Another plant hormone ethylene promotes germination restricting inhibitory effects of ABA (Miransari and Smith 2014). Some other mechanisms are production of osmoprotectant organic molecules like malate, proline and increase in GA/ABA ratio under salinity stress (Ucarli, 2020).

Conclusions

Based on results of the present study, the following conclusions may be drawn:

- Final germination percentage, salinity tolerant index for germination percentage and mean daily germination percentage of linseed were reduced considerably due to salinity (NaCl) stress at 8 dS m⁻¹ or higher levels.
- The abiotic stress delayed germination initial time, and extended maximum germination time and germination duration time in linseed genotypes. However, the responses of all genotypes tested in the present investigation to salinity stress were not consistent with NaCl levels.
- Among 29 genotypes, 80.00% or higher germination was observed in BD-10708 and Lin-1403 up to 16 dS m⁻¹, and Neela, BD-10698, BD-10707, Lin-1203, Lin-W-17 and Lin-2403 up to 12 dS m⁻¹. The pooled mean of these eight genotypes were also 80% or more. These were noted as the most salinity tolerant materials.

Acknowledgement

The first author gratefully acknowledges the Kshrishi Gobeshana Foundation, Bangladesh Agricultural Research Council, Dhaka, Bangladesh for providing fund for the research project and scholarship to work attentively in the project. The first author would like to express her gratitude to the Director-General, Bangladesh Agricultural Research Institute (BARI), and Director, Oilseed Research Center, BARI, Gazipur, Bangladesh for granting deputation to work in the project. She also gratefully acknowledges the Genetic Resource Division, BARI for providing the linseed genotypes.

References

- Abbasian, A., & Moemeni, J. (2013). Effects of salinity stress on seed germination and seedling vigor indices of two halophytic plant species (*Agropyron elongatum* and *A. pectiniforme*). *International Journal of Agriculture and Crop Sciences*, 5(22), 2669–2676.
- Abido, W. A. E., & Zsombik, L. (2019). Effect of salinity on germination characters and seedlings parameters of Egyptian flax cultivars growing in Nyiregyhaza. *Acta Ecologica Sinica*, 39(1), 102–108. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chnaes.2018.05.001>
- Ahsan, M. (2010). *Saline soil of Bangladesh*. Soil Resource Development Institute, SRMAF Project, Ministry of Agriculture, Government of the People's Republic of Bangladesh.
- Ali, M. A., Ahmed, S. M., & Mahmood, S. A. (2022). Effect of NaCl on the germination and growth parameters of some flax varieties (*Linum usitatissimum* L.). *Euphytica Journal of Agricultural Sciences*, 14(1), 98–105.
- Al-Madhagy, S., Ashmawy, N. S., Mamdouh, A. O., Eldahshan, A., & Farag, M. A. (2023). A comprehensive review of the health benefits of flaxseed oil in relation to its chemical composition and comparison with other omega-3-rich oils. *European Journal of Medical Research*, 28(1), 240. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40001-023-01168-8>
- Day, S., Cıkılı, S. Y., & Kaya, M. D. (2018). Screening of some linseed (*Linum usitatissimum* L.) genotypes under salinity stress based on germination and emergence tests. *International Journal of Agriculture and Natural Sciences*, 1(2), 80–86.

- Han, C., & Yang, P. F. (2015). Studies on the molecular mechanisms of seed germination. *Proteomics*, 15, 1671–1679.
- Hefny, Y. A. M., Mohamed, N. E., Abdelraoof, A. O., & Sleem, H. A. (2020). Germination parameters of some bread wheat genotypes under drought stress conditions. *SVU-International Journal of Agricultural Sciences*, 2(2), 226–241. <https://doi.org/10.21608/svuijas.2020.40227.1029>
- Kaya, M. D., Day, S., Cikili, S. Y., & Arslan, N. (2012). Classification of some linseed (*Linum usitatissimum* L.) genotypes for salinity tolerance using germination, seedling growth, and ion content. *Chilean Journal of Agricultural Research*, 72(1), 27–32.
- Kocak, M. Z., Gore, M., & Kurt, O. (2022). The effect of different salinity levels on germination development of some flax (*Linum usitatissimum* L.) varieties. *Turkish Journal of Agriculture and Food Science and Technology*, 10(4), 657–662. <https://doi.org/10.24925/turjaf.v10i4.657-662.4758>
- Kumar, P., Singh, R., Kumar, R. R., Nityanand, Kumar, D., Sohane, R. K., Singh, A. K., & Mehta, S. (2019). Varietal evaluation of different genotypes of linseed for yield performance in Aurangabad district of Bihar. *Current Journal of Applied Science and Technology*, 33(3), 1–4.
- Miransari, M., & Smith, D. (2014). Plant hormones and seed germination. *Environmental and Experimental Botany*, 99, 110–121. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envexpbot.2013.11.008>
- Moghaddam, M., Babaei, K., & Pooya, E. S. (2018). Germination and growth response of flax (*Linum usitatissimum*) to salinity stress and concentrations. *Journal of Plant Nutrition*, 41(5), 563–573. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01904167.2017.1365913>
- Mohammadi, M., Pouryousef, M., & Farhang, N. (2023). Study on germination and seedling growth of various ecotypes of fennel (*Foeniculum vulgare* Mill.) under salinity stress. *Journal of Applied Research on Medicinal and Aromatic Plants*, 34, 100471. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jarmap.2023.100471>
- Muhammad, Z., & Hussain, F. (2010). Effect of NaCl salinity on the germination and seedling growth of some medicinal plants. *Pakistan Journal of Botany*, 42(2), 889–897.
- Munns, R., & Tester, M. (2008). Mechanisms of salinity tolerance. *Annual Review of Plant Biology*, 59, 651–681. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.arplant.59.032607.092911>
- Nasri, N., Maatallah, S., Saidi, I., & Lachaal, M. (2017). Influence of salinity on germination, seedling growth, ion content and acid phosphatase activities of *Linum usitatissimum* L. *The Journal of Animal & Plant Sciences*, 27(2), 517–521.
- Pervez, S., Rauf, M., Gul, H., Yousaf, M. J., & Ali, F. (2021). Comparative study on effect of salinity on seed germination and seedling growth of different *Linum usitatissimum* varieties. *Natural Journal of Biological Sciences*, 2(II), 49–66.
- Ucarli, C. (2020). Effects of salinity on seed germination and early seedling stage. In S. Fahad, S. Saud, Y. Chen, C. Wu, & D. Wang (Eds.), *Abiotic Stress in Plants* (pp. 1–27). IntechOpen. <https://doi.org/10.5772/intechopen.93647>
- Yasar, M., & Yetissin, Y. (2023). Determination of tolerances of some flax varieties to different doses of salt concentrations in early development period. *MAS Journal of Applied Physical Sciences*, 8(1), 144–157. <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7698369>
- Zaghoudi, M., Baatour, O., Bensalem, N., & Abidi, Z. O. (2015). Effect of saline conditions on germination and enzymatic activity in two varieties of *Linum usitatissimum* seeds. *Journal of New Sciences*, 17(6), 529–538.

Appendix: Table 1. Effects of five salinity levels (NaCl solution) on final germination percentage and mean daily germination percentage of twenty nine linseed genotypes under controlled conditions in Petri dish

	Germination percentage (GP)					Pooled mean	Genotype	Mean daily germination % (MDG)					Pooled (PI) mean
	0 dsm ⁻¹	4 dsm ⁻¹	8 dsm ⁻¹	12 dSm ⁻¹	16 dsm ⁻¹			0 dsm ⁻¹	4 dsm ⁻¹	8 dsm ⁻¹	12 dSm ⁻¹	16dsm ⁻¹	
Neela	98.33	87.00	85.00	83.00	67.00	84.00	Neela	25.42	19.51	17.01	16.67	13.33	18.39
BD-7141	90.00	82.00	75.00	60.00	52.00	71.67	BD-7141	30.00	27.23	18.75	20.03	17.22	22.65
BD-7142	93.33	83.00	76.65	62.00	55.00	74.00	BD-7142	29.03	27.78	23.75	19.31	18.33	23.64
BD-7143	91.65	78.00	72.00	58.00	47.00	69.33	BD-7143	26.80	26.11	23.88	19.44	15.55	22.36
BD-7146	91.65	85.00	80.00	52.00	38.00	69.33	BD-7146	27.63	30.00	28.34	28.34	26.67	28.20
BD-10698	98.33	91.65	88.00	83.00	62.00	84.67	BD-10698	20.83	30.55	22.01	27.78	20.56	24.35
BD-10703	91.65	85.00	82.00	75.00	47.00	76.00	BD-10703	28.33	26.11	17.74	22.22	18.88	22.66
BD-10704	85.00	76.65	75.00	67.00	57.00	72.33	BD-10704	30.55	28.34	19.42	25.00	15.55	23.77
BD-10706	88.33	83.00	78.00	72.00	62.00	76.67	BD-10706	23.75	27.78	20.25	23.89	20.56	23.25
BD-10707	95.00	88.00	85.00	82.00	48.00	79.67	BD-10707	29.72	29.45	18.09	27.23	16.11	24.12
BD-10708	95.00	90.00	85.00	85.00	80.00	87.33	BD-10708	28.62	28.34	26.67	17.22	12.78	22.73
BD-10710	91.65	83.00	67.00	53.00	22.00	63.33	BD-10710	26.80	27.78	22.22	17.78	7.23	20.36
Lin-303	91.65	85.00	78.00	53.00	48.00	71.33	Lin-303	22.91	21.26	19.58	13.33	9.67	17.35
Lin-503	95.00	91.65	83.00	75.00	48.00	79.00	Lin-503	22.11	30.00	20.84	26.67	15.56	23.04
Lin-703	91.65	82.00	75.00	52.00	47.00	69.33	Lin-703	22.91	20.43	18.74	12.92	9.33	16.87
Lin-803	83.00	75.00	62.00	55.00	37.00	62.00	Lin-803	24.03	15.92	12.33	16.12	7.33	15.15
Lin-1203	96.65	90.00	85.00	82.00	57.00	82.00	Lin-1203	24.16	30.00	28.34	27.23	18.89	25.72
Lin-1303	96.65	88.00	78.00	50.00	45.00	71.67	Lin-1303	24.16	22.01	19.56	12.50	7.33	17.11
Lin-1403	96.65	91.65	85.00	83.00	80.00	87.33	Lin-1403	22.91	22.91	21.26	20.84	16.00	20.78
Lin-1503/2	93.33	82.00	83.00	80.00	48.00	77.33	Lin-1503/2	31.11	27.23	16.67	15.33	16.12	21.29
Lin-1507/2	91.65	87.00	82.00	76.65	57.00	78.67	Lin-1507/2	22.91	21.67	20.23	19.16	14.17	19.63
Lin-1903	82.00	76.65	67.00	52.00	38.00	63.32	Lin-1903	23.75	25.55	22.23	17.23	11.95	20.14
Lin-2403	95.00	88.00	85.00	82.00	50.00	80.00	Lin-2403	22.67	18.84	17.00	16.34	10.00	16.97
Lin-C-16	81.00	78.00	73.00	52.00	43.00	65.67	Lin-C-16	27.23	26.11	16.49	17.22	14.44	20.30
Lin-C-17	76.65	72.00	65.00	53.00	48.00	63.00	Lin-C-17	19.16	17.92	16.26	13.33	9.67	15.27
Lin-S-19	90.00	85.00	82.00	81.67	48.00	77.00	Lin-S-19	22.50	21.26	14.28	20.00	12.08	18.02
Lin-V-18	95.00	87.00	80.00	55.00	33.00	70.00	Lin-V-18	23.74	23.35	17.00	13.75	8.33	17.23
Lin-W-17	93.33	88.00	82.00	82.00	63.00	81.67	Lin-W-17	22.94	17.67	16.34	16.34	12.66	17.19
Chilmari	76.65	70.00	60.00	48.00	43.00	59.67	Chilmari	25.55	23.33	20.00	26.67	14.45	22.00
Pooled mean	90.89	83.80	77.70	67.10	50.60	74.02	Pooled mean	25.05	24.64	19.84	19.29	14.22	20.71
LSD (P≤0.05) : genotype = 3.95, Salinity = 1.64, Genotype*Salinity = 8.83							LSD (P≤0.05: Genotypes = 1.458, Salinity = 0.606, Genotypes*Salinity = 3.261						

Appendix: Effects of five salinity levels (NaCl solution) on salt tolerant index (STI) for germination and on germination initial time (GIT) of twenty nine linseed genotypes under controlled conditions in Petri dish

	Salt tolerance index (STI) of germination in percentage				Pooled mean	Genotype	Germination initial time % (GIT) in days					Pooled (PI) mean
	4 dsm ⁻¹	8 dsm ⁻¹	12 dSm ⁻¹	16 dsm ⁻¹			0 dsm ⁻¹	4 dsm ⁻¹	8 dsm ⁻¹	12 dSm ⁻¹	16dsm ⁻¹	
Neela	88.23	86.44	84.77	67.62	81.76	Neela	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00	3.00	2.20
BD-7141	89.77	82.45	66.26	58.87	74.34	BD-7141	2.00	2.00	2.25	2.00	2.00	2.05
BD-7142	94.07	82.18	63.88	46.59	71.68	BD-7142	2.00	2.00	2.5 0	2.00	2.00	2.00
BD-7143	85.59	78.31	63.74	51.24	69.72	BD-7143	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00
BD-7146	93.08	87.69	56.46	41.48	69.68	BD-7146	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00
BD-10698	93.22	89.89	84.89	62.63	82.66	BD-10698	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00
BD-10703	92.42	88.42	78.30	66.71	81.46	BD-10703	2.00	2.00	3.0 0	2.00	2.00	2.00
BD-10704	92.87	89.16	82.02	50.97	78.75	BD-10704	2.00	2.00	3.00	2.00	2.00	2.20
BD-10706	94.51	89.15	81.14	70.02	83.71	BD-10706	2.00	2.00	2.25	2.00	2.00	2.05
BD-10707	93.12	89.55	85.97	50.97	79.90	BD-10707	2.25	2.25	2.25	2.00	2.25	2.20
BD-10708	94.79	89.55	89.55	84.31	89.55	BD-10708	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00
BD-10710	92.88	74.72	59.54	24.11	62.81	BD-10710	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00
Lin-303	92.87	85.45	58.39	52.62	72.33	Lin-303	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.25	2.00	2.05
Lin-503	96.68	89.51	85.94	50.13	80.57	Lin-503	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.50	2.75	2.25
Lin-703	89.16	81.88	56.47	51.11	69.65	Lin-703	2.00	2.00	2.25	2.25	2.00	2.10
Lin-803	90.79	92.72	89.01	53.71	81.56	Lin-803	2.00	2.00	2.5 0	2.25	3.00	2.31
Lin-1203	93.23	88.11	84.54	58.82	81.18	Lin-1203	2.00	2.00	2.00	3.00	2.00	2.20
Lin-1303	91.445	80.90	51.56	46.56	67.63	Lin-1303	2.00	2.00	2.25	2.00	2.00	2.05
Lin-1403	94.90	88.11	86.45	82.87	88.08	Lin-1403	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.75	2.50	2.25
Lin-1503/2	91.31	78.43	63.46	56.64	72.46	Lin-1503/2	2.00	2.00	2.5 0	2.00	2.75	2.19
Lin-1507/2	94.66	89.16	83.67	61.69	82.29	Lin-1507/2	2.00	2.00	3.0 0	2.00	2.00	2.00
Lin-1903	94.64	90.93	89.01	53.84	82.10	Lin-1903	2.00	2.00	2.5 0	2.00	2.00	2.00
Lin-2403	90.24	73.61	63.00	43.87	67.68	Lin-2403	2.00	2.00	2.0 0	3.00	3.00	2.50
Lin-C-16	95.99	89.90	63.30	52.88	79.90	Lin-C-16	2.50	2.50	2.50	2.25	2.50	2.45
Lin-C-17	93.58	85.06	69.53	63.08	77.81	Lin-C-17	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.25	2.75	2.20
Lin-S-19	93.21	89.76	86.17	53.00	80.54	Lin-S-19	2.00	2.00	3.0 0	3.00	2.00	2.25
Lin-V-18	91.21	84.43	57.99	35.37	67.25	Lin-V-18	2.00	2.00	3.0 0	2.00	2.00	2.00
Lin-W-17	96.45	89.16	89.16	69.38	86.04	Lin-W-17	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00	3.00	2.20
Chilmari	90.92	83.23	67.02	57.40	74.65	Chilmari	2.00	2.00	2.0 0	2.00	2.00	2.00
Pooled mean	92.62	85.79	73.83	55.81		Pooled mean	2.02	2.02	2.30	2.22	2.26	2.13
LSD(P≤0.05) : Genotype = 5.259, Salinity = 1.959, Genotypes*Salinity = 10.518						LSD (P≤0.05: Genotype = 0.1512, Salinity = 0.0628, Genotype*Salinity = 0.338						

Appendix: Table 3. Effects of five salinity levels (NaCl solution) on maximum germination time (A) and germination duration time (GDT) of twenty nine linseed genotypes under controlled conditions in Petri dish

A: Maximum germination time (MGT) in days under five levels of salinity							B: Germination duration time (GDT) in days under five levels of salinity						
Genotype	0 dS m ⁻¹	4 dS m ⁻¹	8dS m ⁻¹	12 dSm ⁻¹	16 dSm ⁻¹	Pooled mean	Genotype	0 dS/m	4 dS/m	8 dS/m	12 dS/m	16 dS/m	Pooled mean
Neela	4.00	4.50	5.00	5.00	5.00	4.70	Neela	2.00	2.50	3.00	2.00	2.00	2.30
BD-7141	3.00	3.00	4.00	3.25	3.00	3.20	BD-7141	1.00	1.00	2.00	1.00	1.00	1.20
BD-7142	3.25	3.00	3.25	3.00	3.00	3.10	BD-7142	1.00	1.00	1.20	1.20	1.00	1.08
BD-7143	3.50	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.10	BD-7143	1.50	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.10
BD-7146	3.25	3.00 j	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.05	BD-7146	1.25	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.05
BD-10698	4.75	3.00	4.00	3.00	3.00	3.55	BD-10698	2.75	1.00	2.00	1.00	1.00	1.55
BD-10703	3.00	3.00	4.25	3.00	3.00	3.25	BD-10703	1.25	1.25	1.50	1.25	1.25	1.30
BD-10704	3.00	3.00	4.25	3.00	3.00	3.25	BD-10704	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.25	1.25	1.10
BD-10706	3.00	3.00	4.00	3.00	3.00	3.35	BD-10706	1.75	1.00	1.75	1.00	1.00	1.30
BD-10707	3.25	3.00	4.75	3.00	3.00	3.40	BD-10707	1.25	1.00	2.50	1.00	1.00	1.35
BD-10708	3.50	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.10	BD-10708	1.75	1.25	1.25	1.25	1.50	1.40
BD-10710	3.50	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.10	BD-10710	1.25	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.05
Lin-303	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	5.00	4.20	Lin-303	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00	3.00	2.20
Lin-503	4.50	3.00	4.00	3.00	3.00	3.50	Lin-503	2.00	1.00	1.75	1.00	1.50	1.45
Lin-703	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	5.00	4.20	Lin-703	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00	3.00	2.20
Lin-803	3.50	4.75	5.00	3.25	5.00	4.30	Lin-803	1.50	2.75	2.75	1.25	2.00	2.05
Lin-1203	4.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.20	Lin-1203	2.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.20
Lin-1303	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	5.00	4.20	Lin-1303	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00	3.00	2.20
Lin-1403	4.25	4.00	4.00	4.00	5.00	4.25	Lin-1403	2.00	2.00	1.75	2.00	2.50	2.05
Lin-1503/2	3.00	3.00	5.00	5.25	3.00	3.85	Lin-1503/2	1.00	1.00	2.00	2.75	1.00	1.55
Lin-1507/2	4.00	4.00	4.25	4.00	4.00	4.05	Lin-1507/2	2.00	2.00	1.75	2.00	2.00	1.95
Lin-1903	3.50	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.25	3.15	Lin-1903	1.50	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.10
Lin-2403	4.25	4.75	5.00	5.00	5.00	4.80	Lin-2403	2.25	2.50	3.00	2.00	2.00	2.35
Lin-C-16	3.00	3.00	4.50	3.00	3.00	3.30	Lin-C-16	1.00	1.25	1.50	1.00	1.00	1.15
Lin-C-17	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	5.00	4.20	Lin-C-17	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00	3.00	2.20
Lin-S-19	4.00	4.00	5.75	4.00	4.00	4.35	Lin-S-19	2.00	2.00	2.75	2.00	2.00	2.15
Lin-V-18	4.00	3.75	4.75	4.00	4.00	4.10	Lin-V-18	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00
Lin-W-17	4.25	5.00	5.00	5.00	5.00	4.85	Lin-W-17	2.25	3.00	3.00	2.00	2.00	2.45
Chilmari	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	Chilmari	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Pool mean	3.71	3.57	4.08	3.64	3.81	3.73	Pooled mean	1.66	1.53	1.80	1.48	1.62	1.62
LSD (P≤0.05) Genotype = 0.175, Salinity = 0.0727, Genotype*Salinity = 0.391							LSD (P≤0.05) Genotype = 0.359, Salinity = 0.177, Genotype*Salinity = 0.951.						

